

PSYCHOCULTURAL AND ECONOMIC DETERMINATIONS OF
ANTREPRENORIAL BEHAVIORDETERMINĂRI PSIHO-CULTURALE ȘI ECONOMICE ALE
COMPORTAMENTULUI ANTREPRENORIAL**Maria-Cristina, STOICA**

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Abstract

The paper analyses some psychological and cultural determinants of Romanian entrepreneurship. The underlying hypothesis is that some psychological and cultural personalities are more prone to entrepreneurship than other segments of the population. Individuals with a certain psychological and cultural profile can have or acquire entrepreneurial skills, risk inclination, by virtue of personality traits. The work has scientifically demonstrated the existence or absence of significant links between personality traits, culture, economical context and entrepreneurship. Currently, the economic crisis is accelerating, and the concerns for future uncertainties are spreading throughout our society

Keywords: psychological and cultural traits, entrepreneurship, education**Rezumat**

Lucrarea analizează unele determinări psihologice și culturale ale antreprenoriatului românesc. Ipoteza care stă la baza este că unele personalități psihologice și culturale sunt mai predispuse la antreprenoriat decât alte segmente ale populației. Persoanele cu un anumit profil psihologic și cultural pot avea sau dobândi abilități antreprenoriale, înclinație de risc, în virtutea trăsăturilor de personalitate. Lucrarea a demonstrat științific existența sau absența unor legături semnificative între trăsăturile de personalitate, cultură, contextul economic și antreprenoriat. În prezent, criza economică se accelerează, iar preocupările pentru incertitudinile viitoare se răspândesc în întreaga societate.

Cuvinte - cheie: trăsături psihologice și culturale, antreprenoriat, educație.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is the process that continually prepares individuals for an uncertain and complex society, which promotes the attentive and attractive person, intelligently rational and emotional. As a field of study, entrepreneurship is relatively recent, but important for the evolution of society. The entrepreneur is the individual who capitalizes on a business opportunity / or has an idea for which he or she risks, acquires the necessary resources, initiates the project and assumes responsibility for its continuation. Entrepreneurs represent a heterogeneous category of individuals who can be successful in the most diverse fields of activity. The entrepreneur forms an organization that expects to create value for exchange and not just its own consumption. Entrepreneurs are the agents of change, they take the risk and make new combinations [17]. They bring to life a vision, a dream. They are nonconformist and observe the possibilities and not the problems caused by change. Entrepreneurship is the transformation of an idea into opportunity and opportunity in creation. The economic context is an important determinant, but psych cultural research on this topic is current, necessary and contributes to the development of entrepreneurial skills necessary for those who take responsibility for a business.

The paper aims at identifying the psycho-cultural and economic determinations that underpin the entrepreneurial behavior [9; 11; 8]. The underlying hypothesis is that some people are more psychologically and culturally inclined towards entrepreneurship than other segments of the

population. Some individuals may have or acquire entrepreneurial skills due to personality traits. This paper demonstrates scientifically the existence or absence of significant links between psychological and cultural features and entrepreneurial behavior.

The paper highlights the importance of the economic context for the Romanian entrepreneurial behavior. Psychological and cultural researches on entrepreneurial behavior are important for stimulating initiative, proactive education, innovation and creativity. The results of some studies [6] reveal that the start in the process of identifying business opportunities is given by the knowledge and information acquired through education and practical experience. Individuals with some experience and a certain educational standard are more receptive to changes in society and more skilled in identifying entrepreneurial opportunities. The results of some important studies confirm the hypothesis that entrepreneurs discover business opportunities by developing psycho-cultural abilities, thus enhancing their capacity to identify other opportunities by others even before they are visible [18, p.7]. The study of psychological and cultural determinants for entrepreneurial behavior is part of the trend of the latest research that has moved from the question “what is the entrepreneur” to the question “which factors are determinants for entrepreneurial behavior” [16; 5].

The psychological and cultural outlook on entrepreneurial behavior has highlighted the fact that there are some common traits common to entrepreneurs such as the need to achievement, the in-

ternal locus of control, risk-taking, the acceptance of uncertainty, the opening to change, the need for autonomy [3; 17; 7]. The research has shown that beyond the personality traits, entrepreneurship is more influenced by culture, the economic environment and education.

Empirical research

Purpose, objectives and hypotheses of research

The research aims to analyze the correlation between psycho-cultural and economic determinants of entrepreneurial behavior.

Objectives

1. Establishing the correlation between the need for achievement, locus of control (self-efficacy) and entrepreneurial behavior.
2. Relationship between Uncertainty Avoidance Culture and Entrepreneurial Behaviour.
3. To analyze the influence of the Masculinity-Femininity cultural dimension on entrepreneurial behavior.
4. Determine the correlation between the economic context and the entrepreneurial behaviour.

General hypothesis

Entrepreneurial behavior is influenced by psych cultural features and economic context.

Experimental hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant correlation between need for achievement, locus of control and the entrepreneurial behavior.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant correlation between Uncertainty Avoidance Culture and entrepreneurial behavior.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant correlation between the gender of respondents and entrepreneurial behavior.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant correlation between the economic context and the entrepreneurial behaviour.

The sample

The research analysed the results obtained from a sample of 187 respondents. The age of the subjects ranges from 19 to 50 years (30 subjects aged 20-30), 98 are women and 89 are men. Respondents work or have worked for at least one year. The sample includes people working in public administration (82), trade (42), education (28) and IT (35). Respondents are from the urban area and the city of Iasi, which according to the statistical data provided by the National Institute of Statistics (<http://www.insse.ro>) had a population of 361845 in 2015, of which 173019 (47.82) men and 188826 (52.18%) women. The representativeness was also achieved by the criteria: the field of activity and the type of organization (insee.ro).

Table no. 1.

Representativeness by field of activity

	Activities	%
1	Public Administration	43,85
2	Commerce	22,46

3	Education	14,97
4	IT	18,72
	TOTAL	100

Fig. 1. The graphic representation of the observation units by type of activity.

Table 2.

Representativeness by public and private

	Public and Private Property	%
1.	Public	58,82
2.	Private	41,18
	TOTAL	100

Table 3.

Representativeness by gender

	Respondents by gender	%
1	Women	52,18
2	Men	47,82
	TOTAL	100

Design of research

Study variables:

Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurial Behavior

Independent variables: Need for achievement, locus of control (self-efficacy)

Experiment:

To study the effects of each independent variable (main effects) and interaction, a factorial design of the 2X2 type was made, which means that each of the two factors has two levels and four different conditions [10].

Need for achievement

Methodology:

→ Questionnaires: control locus, avoidance of uncertainty, entrepreneurial behavior

→ Statistical analysis: ANOVA, Levene Test, SPSS

→ Qualitative analysis

Tools

The 32 items are 32 statements that the subjects rank according to the extent to which they agree on a 6-step scale in which: 1 = never true; 2 = very rarely true; 3 = sometimes true; 4 = often true; 5 = very often true; 6 = always true.

The *Cronbach's alpha* (a coefficient of reliability) on the whole questionnaire was 0.872.

We used Control Locus Questionnaire (LOC Rotter, 1966) and need for achievement theory (McClelland, 1961). McClelland says that, regardless of our gender, culture, or age, we all have some motivating factors, and one of these will be dominant. This dominant motivator is largely dependent on our culture and life experiences. The need for Achievement suppose that:

→ An individual has a strong need to set and accomplish challenging goals.

→ Takes calculated risks to accomplish their goals.

→ Likes to receive regular feedback on their progress and achievements.

→ Often likes to work alone.

Locus of control concept defines how a person explains their success or failure through internal or external causes, controllable or uncontrollable. There is a dichotomizing of this concept: the internal control locus (low scores) implies the belief that power and personal control can influence events, that their own success is due to the skills and work done, and the external control locus (high scores) refers to the belief that personal power has a minimal effect on events, caused by the destiny or the power of others. Some studies have displayed a positive association between locus of control and educational achievement [13].

→ The questionnaire contains 40 items (13 in the model questionnaire)

→ The internal consistency coefficient is 0.79.

Entrepreneurial behavioural questionnaire (adaptation after Pinte, 2007)

It is a questionnaire with 4 items that targets the intention of people to open their own business. Responses were given on a five-level Likert – scale (<https://www.simplypsychology.org>), as follows: Strongly Agree, Agree, Sometimes, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree

→ The internal consistency ratio is 0.88.

Findings

To test the hypotheses we used univariate ANOVA test (<https://statistics.>). Tables no. 4, 5, 6 presents the results of the statistical analysis.

Need to achievement Group

Table 4.

Entrepreneurial behaviour according to the need to achievement

Need for achievement	Mean	Std. Error	Confidence interval 95%	
			Lower bound	Upper bound
Low	10,309	,514	9,290	11,327
High	10,932	,526	9,890	11,974

Locus of control Group

Table 5.

Locus of control in Entrepreneurial Behaviour

Need for achievement	Mean	Std. Error	Confidence interval 95%	
			Lower bound	Upper bound
Low	11,174	,514	10,156	12,193
High	10,067	,526	9,025	11,109

Table 6.

Effects of independent variables on Entrepreneurial Behaviour

Group	F	df	Sig.
Need for achievement	2,26	1	0,135
Locus of control	0,71	1	0,398
Locus of control*Need	0,31	1	0,576
Total	F	112	

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1: It is found that there is no significant effect of the variable need to achieve on entrepreneurial behavior.

$F(1,112) = 0,7$, with $p = 0,398$. Since $p > 0,05$ the hypothesis is not confirmed, which means that the entrepreneurial in-

tervention is not influenced by the level of need for achievement.

Table 4 shows that there is no significant effect either of the locus of control variable on entrepreneurial behavior.

F (1,112) = 2, 26 with p = 0,135. Since p> 0.05, the hypothesis is not confirmed, which means that the entrepreneurial behavior is not influenced by the locus of control.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant correlation between Uncertainty Avoidance Culture and entrepreneurial behavior.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant correlation between the gender of respondents and entrepreneurial behavior.

To test if the independent variables influence the dependent variable, the T (SPSS, statistics) (SPSS, statistics) test was applied. The obtained results are presented in tables 7.

Table 7.
Effects of independent variables on Entrepreneurial Behaviour

Variables	F	df	Sig.	t
Uncertainty Avoidance	0,74	116	0,06	1,88
Gender of respondents	3,49	118	0,61	-0,50

Hypothesis no. 2.

Research hypothesis:

Subjects with a high level of uncertainty avoidance have a different behavior than subjects with a high level of uncertainty acceptance.

Null hypothesis:

Respondents are not influenced by the Uncertainty.

Subjects avoiding uncertainty: Mgr1 = 11, 2,

Subjects accepting uncertainty: Mgr2 = 9, 83

The Levene’s test (Levene, 1960) has the value: F = 0, 74; p = 0, 38

The value of t (116) = 1, 88; p = 0, 06

Since p> 0, 05, the null hypothesis is accepted and the research hypothesis is rejected.

Table 8.
Independent Samples Test for UA

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
		F	Sig
Entrep. Behaviour	Equal variances assumed	,748	,389
	Equal variances not assumed		

t-test for Equality of Means						
t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
1,909	116	,059	1,36979	,71767	,05165	2,79123
1,887	106,321	,062	1,36979	,72582	,06917	2,80875

Hypothesis no. 3

Research hypothesis:

Male respondents have different entrepreneurial behaviours than females.

Null hypothesis:

Respondents are not gender-sensitive
 It is noted that there are no significant differences in entrepreneurial behaviour between male and female subjects.

Environments: Female subjects-Mgr1 = 10, 41,

Male subjects-Mgr2 = 10, 77

The Levene test has the value of F = 3, 49; p = 0, 06

The value of t (118) = -0, 50; p = 0, 61

Since p > 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted and the research hypothesis is denied.

Hypothesis no.4. There is a significant correlation between the economic context and the entrepreneurial behavior.

Table 9.

The factors that inhibit the entrepreneurial behavior

The factors	%
Instability and suspicion	100
Taxes levels	100
Tax unpredictability	100
Excessive bureaucracy	99
Corruption	99
Black market	93
Income levels	90
Access to finance	93
Education	77
Mentality and fear of failure	47

Entrepreneurial behavior was analyzed from the perspective of the economic and social context [9; 1; 2]. through a qu-

estionnaire with 8 items. The factors that inhibit the entrepreneurial behavior are represented in table 9 and graph 2.

Fig. 2. Inhibitors of entrepreneurial behavior.

Conclusions

The results do not confirm that the psych cultural variables analyzed influence the entrepreneurial behavior. The need for achievement shows the desire to excel, being defined as a competitive behavior. The locus of control is a trait that refers to perceived control over general situations, while entrepreneurial behavior manifests itself in specific situations requiring knowledge, skills, and competencies. Studies that have highlighted a significant relationship of this trait with entrepreneurship may have operationalized the locus of control s by reference to entrepreneurial situations. Owning entrepreneurial personality traits does not automatically mean that an individual will develop entrepreneurial behavior. Is possible that this potential materializes in

entrepreneurial behavior when a trigger event occurs, such as job loss or a market opportunity. Respondents' behavior is guided by attitudes that are in line with the current context, with attitudes being formed by learning roles.

People think they have control over what is happening to them because of the knowledge of service duties, a belief invalidated by the knowledge and attention economy, a world that no longer offers stability and security. Entrepreneurial behavior can also be explained from the perspective of the theory of social learning (Bandura in McLeod, 2016), namely that those who have an entrepreneurial model around them or learn about it, may want to take risks, innovation. At the same time, the perception of the subjects is influenced by important people in their lives,

culture, customs, stereotypes, income. Income levels and the state of the economy can influence entrepreneurial behavior. The study included respondents who have never established a business. The need for achievement did not lead to a favorable attitude towards entrepreneurial behavior.

The inclination towards entrepreneurship is a mix of organizational and individual factors. Statistics show that many people in Romania are pursuing safety, stability and prestige. Public organizations meet traditional, conformist individuals who adopt the values and norms of their organization. Their primary purpose is to maintain the balance and tranquility of professional and family life. The motivation of non-entrepreneurial behaviour is given by the need to have a job.

The research highlights through the lack of correlation between the stated variables that people make choices according to the environment they live in, attitudes, beliefs, socio-cultural values inherited and transmitted through a certain cultural model, traditionalist in Romania. The Romanian cultural model is collectivist and focuses on family, work, religion [3, p.180].

The analysis of the need to achievement as an independent variable that influences entrepreneurial behaviour highlights the labour market crisis, the decline in professional motivation. Statistics (www.insse.ro), show that in Iasi, a county with economic growth below the country's average, people are looking for a job without taking into account the profession once chosen. People are looking for stability, security and a salary. Jobs have fallen, so the ambition to follow a certain

career has gone. In the public domain, most are based on a training that has nothing to do with the new job. Both men and women reduced their ambition, their need to achievement at work. Standard subsistence or evolution has become essential concerns. Against the background of the economic and political crisis, women and men only want a job, even if it does not provide them with fulfilment.

Qualifications, specializations, trainings are required by regulations and are made with the aim of gaining diplomas that allow advancement and a better salary. The collective model also highlights the trend of respondents in IT and education. The analysis of the questionnaires highlighted the desire to achievement at a high level, the ambition to perform, curiosity, openness to the new and creativity. From the statistical analysis of this topic results that the need for achievement is found in close proportions to men and women, a finding that positions the Romanian organizations in the middle, considering the masculinity-femininity scale. The study confirms the results of Hofstede, but also of other specialists. For collective entrepreneurial behavior, the need for realization has no significant influence. Concerning the uncertainty avoidance, the study shows that the respondents confirm the Romanian collective profile [14; 3].

Respondents demonstrate resistance to change, a poor autonomy, and inferiority complex. They are envious of the others and more preoccupied with gossip than well done work or innovation [14, p. 327]. Most subjects work in the public sector, statistics highlighting the media. The study shows that the entrepreneurial

behavior in Iasi is not influenced by the psycho-cultural characteristics analysed. “The Romanians’ psycho-cultural profile is dominated by the lack of confidence that may have been born on the backdrop of the uncertainty of the long of history” [3].

The conclusion from the experiment shows the collective behavior of a group that is representative of the employees in Iasi (www.insse.ro). Most of the respondents is working in the public organizations; this environment is not the most suitable for the creative, innovative individual.

Representative research [3]. has highlighted that private respondents, especially those in IT, are inclined towards individualism and acceptance of uncertainty, which means the focus on autonomy found in most European countries. Important studies have demonstrated that the psycho-cultural profile of young people in Romania is more individualistic compared to the classical profile proposed by Hofstede and his collaborators [8].

From the analysis resulted a strong correlation between the economic and social context and the entrepreneurial behaviour. The Romanian environment is affected by crises, instability, bureaucracy and corruption. Entrepreneurship is not supported by Romanian cultural values and mentalities. Entrepreneurship is a function that is directly proportional to quality and inversely proportional to the cost of production factors [12]. The purpose of the work has been achieved. The research has shown that the determinants of entrepreneurial behavior are economic conditions and the political context.

Limits and perspectives of the research

Due to design choices and circumstances this study has many limitations. Firstly, the entrepreneurial behavior can be better understood by analysing a mix of different: personality, education, culture, economic-social and political context. Each of these has its role and it is difficult to measure the impact of each on the entrepreneurial behaviour. The key issue of any such research is identifying the determinants at a given time. The paper does not deny the role of psycho-cultural factors in entrepreneurship. It only demonstrates on a sample that nowadays, in Romania the main determinant of the entrepreneurship is the state.

Politicians and institutions positively influence the entrepreneurial process through infrastructure, modern, legislative and educational systems. The current political environment cannot start such an influence because it is “tribal and fragmented” [3, p.330]. Secondly, the sample and methods used impose limits on the statistical validity of this study. The data obtained from respondents are incomplete and insufficient to use the most advanced techniques of statistical analysis. For the sample, the participants were selected from one city without being able to compare with other groups. The adopted methodology and psycho-cultural inspiration criteria are not the only possibilities for studying the researched phenomenon. The integration of the information obtained from the research included conclusions from various national and international studies. The limits of research also arise from the depth and breadth of the study.

Future research should use more elaborate tests after more data has been collected. The study of entrepreneurial behavior is a complex challenge, requiring elaborate studies and interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary connections. More educated, including from a cultural perspective, the next entrepreneurs could use more informal institutions to fill in formal or inadequate formal institutions. Entrepreneurial education can make:

- Individuals to be more autonomous, with a high self-esteem.
- Individuals learn about opportunities and constraints on entrepreneurship.
- Individuals develop a socio-cultural context based on trust, solidarity, teams.
- Individuals to bring about paradigm shifts that bring modern, powerful and functional social institutions that allow the wasting of the potential of the Romanian people [3, p.330].

The challenge for future research will be to study the psycho-cultural evolution of educated individuals who will be able to significantly influence their governors and policies in support of Romanian entrepreneurship. This is particularly important for economies in transition, with an uncertain, ambiguous and turbulent institutional framework.

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